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THE IMPLEMENTATION OF K13 CURRICULUM IN MADRASAH ALIYAH IN THE SOUTH WEST REGION OF ACEH (ENGLISH TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES)

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Abstract

Teacher's perception of the K-13 is believed to be one of the factors that lead to the success or failure of the curriculum implementation. This is because the K-13 makes teachers have to adjust and change the learning style in the classroom. Considering the various phenomena about the K-13, the researcher was interested in conducting research the Implementation of the K-13 in the South West Region of Aceh (English Teachers' Perspectives). In this research, the researchers also analyzed some obstacles faced by the English Teachers in implementing the K-13 and what solutions offered by STAIN Teungku Dirundeng Meulaboh as one of the universities which produce the teachers in the South West Region of Aceh. The research applied quantitative and qualitative approach that involved 21 English teachers who teach English at Madrasah across South West of Aceh. The result of the study indicated that the implementation of K-13 has not been effective due to several reasons such as the allocation time is insufficient and too many forms of assessment. Moreover, the English teachers issued that the biggest obstacle in implementing the K-13 was the excessive administrative demands. Therefore, the government of Indonesia, in this matter, the Department of Education has to ascertain that the majority of English teachers receive training related to K-13 and review the time allocation provided to the English teachers. For the English teachers, they should be creative and innovative in improving their understanding on K-13 using printed and online resources.

Keywords: *K-13 Curriculum, English Teachers, Madrasah, South West of Aceh*

Introduction

Today, the development of English Language Learning and Teaching (ELLT) is really unprecedented. In Indonesia, it has been recognized as an essential skill to acquire in order to be successful in a globalized society. Also, it is a core element of the secondary school curriculum, and college students study English to find good jobs after graduation. In short, there is an interest in what it takes to be a successful English language learner. To ensure English learning runs smoothly, the government needs to design a curriculum that will be the foundation of national education goals in Indonesia. The Ministry of Education and Culture reveals that 2013 Curriculum, a means of integrating values systems, knowledge and skills (Diknas, 2013 : 3). It has orientation on developing the learners' competencies, the changing of teaching-learning methodology towards teaching learning process which gives priorities on the learning experiences through observing, inquiring, associating, and communicating so as to enhance the values of competitiveness and build prime characters.

In this matter, the Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia (Diknas, 2013 :4) has determined a set of plans and arrangements for purpose, content, and teaching materials and

methods to guide the implementation of learning activities to achieve specific educational goals. The plans can be used as consideration in developing a curriculum. With such understanding, the curriculum developers can define the scope of work to be done, which is the development of objectives, contents and subject matters, and the process to learn the material.

In addition, the curriculum is a set of subjects and educational programs designed by educational institution containing a lesson plan that will be given to the participants in the education period. The implementation of the K-13 is part of continuing the development of the Competency-Based Curriculum (KBK) which was initiated in 2004 by integrating attitudes, knowledge and skills in an integrated manner. To achieve all of these, the curriculum involves not only exploration, elaboration, confirmation, but also observation, inquiry, analysis, reasoning, description, inference, evaluation and creation (Srijono, 2013 :.221).

Ahmad (2014 :45) figured out that one of the main purposes of this curriculum is to shape the individuals who are faithful in God, good in characters, confident, successful in learning, responsible citizens and positive contributors to the civilization. This idea was supported by Mulyasa (2013 :240) who confirmed that the K-13 is proposed to produce students who have religious tolerance and mental health. The reason is that based on the fact that a lot of young generation or students

do not have character, tolerance and empathy for others anymore. In addition, The K-13 is much more emphasis on building students' characters, developing relevant skills based on students' interests and needs, and developing a thematic approach that benefits students' cognitive abilities (Putra,2014:46). The implementation of Curriculum 2013 mean the acceleration of national development priority to accomplish and perfect and active learning method which is based on culture values of the nation (Ilma & Pratama, 2015 :27).

Basically, there are four elements of change in the K-13, namely Graduates Competency Standards, Content Standards (core competencies and basic competencies), Process Standards, and Assessment Standards. In improving Competency Standards Graduates,it is necessary to consider the development of integrated values, knowledge and skills that focus on achieving competencies. At every level of education, the formulation of the four core competencies (the realization and practice of religion, attitudes, skills and knowledge) is the basis for developing basic competencies in each class (Ilma, & Pratama, 2015 :33)

Each teacher has an individual perception on the K-13 changes. Generally the teacher will be critical and judge whether the change is only theoretical thing and can be done in the classroom or assume that the old curriculum is more meaningful. According to Wulandari (2010 :221),Perception is a process whereby someone chooses, organizes, means the input of information to create a meaningful picture of something. This

perception will depend not only on physical stimuli but also the relationship between stimuli and the field that surrounds one's own condition. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (1996:270), Perception is the process by which individuals organize and interpret the impression of their senses to give meaning to the environment they. The development of the K-13 is part of a strategy to improve educational achievement. The orientation of 2013 curriculum is an improvement and balance between attitude competency, skill and knowledge.

Conceptually the K-13 draft is aspired to be able to formulate a bright future generation that is not only intellectual, but also emotionally, socially and spiritually intelligent. This can be done by integrating character values in the learning process that allow students to construct new knowledge based on learning experiences gained from the classroom, school environment, and community as well will be able to bring students closer to the culture of the people in their nation (Sahiruddin, 2013 :67)

The K-13 is one of the solutions to face the changing times that will later emphasize on competencies that are synergized with character values. According to the Minister of Education and Culture Law No.69 of 2013, the 2013 curriculum aims to prepare Indonesian people to have the ability to live as individuals and citizens who are faithful, productive, creative, innovative, and affective, and able to contribute to the life of society, nation, stateless, and world civilization(Nugraheni, 2015 :53).

A part of that ,Law Number 20 of 2003 states that one of the national education development strategies is the development and implementation of a competency-based curriculum. This shows that there is no stagnation in the curriculum but dynamism which is in accordance with the times. Darmawan (2006 :11) suggested that an increasingly large community towards education and advances in science and technology make education impossible to manage only through traditional patterns. In line with the development of the culture of people's lives, changes in terms of improvement in the field of education need to continue to be carried out in anticipation of the interests of the future by being harmonized with the development of science, technology and art and the needs in the world of work today. Improvements in the field of education in Indonesia certainly have foundations that are used as guidelines by looking at the output of the school to create a qualified education now and in the future.

The Ministry of Education and Culture Regulation N0. 69 (2013) explained that to assess the quality of education in Indonesia can be analyzed by eight criteria, namely content (curriculum), learning process, graduate competence, teaching staff, infrastructure, education management, education funding and education assessment . The curriculum ranks first in the eight criteria which shows that the curriculum has a large role in determining the quality of education in Indonesia.

Education by many people is considered as a determinant of the future of students, therefore a good curriculum based on character is expected to be implemented in Indonesia so that creative and productive learners will be created which will have implications for the progress of the nation and state. The Implementation of the K-13 is predicted as an initial milestone in the progress of the nation because it is emphasized on the activeness of students. However, there are still some problems in the learning process related to the development of contextual subject matter, the application of scientifically based learning methods and the application of authentic assessment techniques. The journey of the curriculum might not go perfectly as it is expected, therefore, continuous improvement efforts in the management of the curriculum in the school and the practice of learning in class becomes important (Depdikbud,2013 :4).

According to Mahanani (2013 :6), the K-13 is a system, having components that are interrelated between one another, namely the objective component, content / teaching materials, strategies or methods, organization, and evaluation. The five components have very important role in learning as the objectives in the curriculum have a decisive role that will direct learning activities and provide color to each other component of the curriculum. Although the curriculum plays a role as the direction, purpose and foundation of the educational philosophy, it must be in accordance with the dynamics of the development

of science and technology, the demands of the labor market needs, and social development in society.

The implementation of the K-13 creates a more interactive learning process which will then lead to more positive growth in productivity, liveliness and character of students and changes in their mindset. Not only to students, teachers are required to improve the quality of learning, develop learning methods, the ability to integrate learning with a scientific approach, and develop student character (Depdikbud., 2014 :34).

On the other hand, Mulyasa (2013 :240) asserted that the implementation of the K-13 greatly reaps the pros and cons because the implementation of the curriculum is not going well and still needs improvement, especially in the teacher's understanding of the K-13. Most teachers claims that they still do not understand the core competencies and basic competencies due to confusion how to teach and assess it. This is also supported by Kurniasih (2014 :33) who mentions a number of shortcomings in the K-13, namely: (1) teachers misunderstood that assuming that the K-13 the teacher did not need to explain the material to students in the classroom, (2) there were many teachers who were not ready mentally with this 2013 curriculum, (3) lack of understanding of teachers with the concept of scientific approach, (4) many teachers do not master authentic assessment, (5) teachers have never been directly involved in the K-13 development process, because the government tends to see teachers and students has the same capacity, (6) the absence of a

balance between the orientation of the learning process and the results in the K-13 because the National Examination is still an inhibiting factor, (7) too much material must be mastered by students so that not every material can be conveyed properly, not to mention the teacher's problems those who are less dedicated to the subjects they teach, (8) student learning burdens and terms the teacher is too heavy, so the study time in school is too long. In general, the K-13 which is being implemented at the high school level or madrasah aliyah still arise some problems related to the development of contextual material, the application of scientific-based learning strategies or methods and the application of authentic techniques. Also, there are schools not developing the learning process by utilizing technology to optimize student learning outcomes, both due to teacher competency factors and limited facilities and infrastructure. Teacher's perception of the K-13 is believed to be one of the factors that lead to the success or failure of the curriculum implementation. This is because the K-13 makes teachers have to adjust and change the learning style in the classroom(Majid,2014). Considering the various phenomena above, the researcher was interested in conducting research on "Perceptions of English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah on the Implementation of the K-13 in the South West Region of Aceh''In his research, the researcher will also analyze some obstacles faced by the English Teachers in implementing the K-13 and what solutions offered by STAIN Teungku Dirundeng Meulaboh as one of the

universities which produce the teachers in the South West Region of Aceh.

Based on the background of the study above, several problems can be formulated as follows:

1. How do English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh perceive the implementation of K-13 ?
2. What are the obstacles faced by English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh in teaching English through K-13 ?

Literature Review

Perception

Perception is a process that involves the entry of messages or information into the human brain (Daryanto, 2009 :110). Humans are created equipped with sensory devices that function to recognize themselves and the outside world, through this sensing process that will bring up the perception of the individual. Humans with their senses do activities of observing, experiencing, and experiencing or giving meaning to all stimuli that come so that individuals are able to respond to what they have. Like Slameto (2003,p.9) suggests that through human perception there is a continuous relationship with his environment. The relationship is carried out through the sense of sight, listener, touch, taste, and smell. Rakhmat and Jalaluddin (2001 :27) proposed that perception is the experience of objects,

events, or relationships obtained by inferring information and interpreting messages. Stimulation experienced by humans both about relationships with someone, as well as about mass events will be concluded and interpreted by the brain, what is experienced by humans is able to be expressed because of using feelings, thinking abilities, and individual experiences that may not be the same between individuals with each other in perceiving it.

Dimiyati (1989 :113) said that perception is an interpretation of the stimulus that is already in the brain. Perception is an assumption that is possessed by humans, humans are created by being equipped with sensory tools to see, feel, hear, feel and smell. As human beings socially unable to live alone, interaction with other human beings is needed, with these things needed the senses to interact with each other even to know things outside of themselves. Walgito (2002 :111) suggested that the definition of perception is a process that organizes and combines our data (sensing) to be developed in such a way that we can realize our surroundings, including self-awareness.

The Definition of Curriculum

The curriculum is a set of subjects taught on specific areas of expertise (KBBI, 2008). Etymologically, the curriculum is derived from the Greek word which means "runner" and *curere* means "place to race". So, the term curriculum in ancient Rome implies a distance that must be traveled by runners from the start line to the finish line. It was only in 1855 that the term curriculum

was used in education which meant a number of subjects in higher education. The curriculum in the classical view was seen as a lesson plan in a school. Lessons and materials must be taken at school that is the curriculum (Hidayat, 2013).

Law Number 20 Year 2003 concerning the national education system states that the curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the objectives, content, and learning materials as well as the methods used to guide the implementation of learning activities to achieve certain educational goals (Permendikbud, 2013) about the basic framework and structure of the curriculum. According to Taba in Nasution (2009) argues, that in essence each curriculum is a way to prepare children to participate as productive members in their community. Each curriculum, no matter the pattern, always has certain components, namely a statement of goals and objectives, selection and organization of materials and content of lessons, forms and teaching and learning activities and finally an evaluation of learning outcomes.

Poerwati (2013) says that various interpretations about the curriculum can be reviewed from another perspective, so we get the following classification:

- a. The curriculum can be seen as a product, for instance as the work of curriculum development, usually in a committee.
- b. The curriculum is also seen as a program, which is a tool used by the school to achieve its goals.

- c. The curriculum can be viewed as things that are expected to be learned by students, namely knowledge, attitudes, certain skills.
- d. Curriculum as student experience. The three views above relate to curriculum planning while this view is about what actually becomes reality for each student.

From the above explanation, the researcher concluded that the curriculum is a set of teaching plans that teachers use as a guide in teaching and learning activities in schools to achieve educational goals.

Understanding The K-13 Curriculum

The k-13 curriculum is competency based students' character education. The character education in the k-13 curriculum aims to improve the quality of the process and results of education, which leads to the formation of students' character as a whole, integrated, and balanced, in accordance with the competency standards of graduates in each education unit (Mulyasa, 2013). Based on this understanding, there are two dimensions of the curriculum, the first is a plan and arrangement of objectives, content, and learning materials, while the second is the way used for learning activities. Imas and Sani (2014) suggested that the K-13 curriculum is a series of improvements to the curriculum that had been initiated in 2004 based on competency and then continued with the 2006 curriculum (KTSP). In other word, Curriculum 2013 is a continuation of the development of a competency-based curriculum that covers the

competency of attitudes, knowledge, and skills in an integrated manner (Hidayat, 2013).

Platform of the K-13 Curriculum

According to the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 69 of 2013, the K-13 Curriculum is based on three foundations ; philosophically, juridically and conceptually :

a) Philosophical foundation

Basically there is no single educational philosophy that can be used specifically for curriculum development that can produce quality human beings.

b) Theoretical Foundation

The K-13 Curriculum was developed based on the theory of " standard-based education, and theory of competency-based curriculum. Standard-based education stipulates the existence of national standards as a minimum quality of society that include content standards, process standards, graduate competency standards, teacher and education personnel standards, facilities and infrastructure standards, management standards, financing standards, and education assessment standards. The competency-based curriculum is designed to provide the broadest learning experience for students in developing the ability to behave, be knowledgeable, be skillful.

The K-13 Curriculum embraces: (1) learning conducted by teachers (taught curriculum) in the form of processes developed in the form of learning activities in schools, classrooms, and the community; and (2) students' direct learning experiences (learned curriculum) according to the background, characteristics, and initial abilities of students. Individual student's direct learning experiences become learning outcomes for themselves, while the learning outcomes of all students become the results of the curriculum. (Permendikbud No 69 Year 2013).

c) Juridical foundation

Juridical foundation for the the K-13 Curriculum is:

1. The 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia;
2. Law Number 20 Year 2003 concerning the Education System National;
3. Law Number 17 of 2005 concerning the National Long-Term Development Plan, along with all the provisions set forth in the National Medium-Term Development Plan; and
4. Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards as amended by Government Regulation Number 32 of 2013 concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 19 of

2005 concerning National Education Standards.
(Permendikbud No 69 Year 2013)

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework describes the relationship between concepts or variables to be studied. The perception conducted by teachers in the the K-13 Curriculum focuses on the implementation of learning English. The concepts to be examined in this study are about the the K-13 Curriculum, the implementation of English learning, and the perception of English teachers. The curriculum aims to develop a balance between developing spiritual and social attitudes, curiosity, creativity, collaboration with intellectual and psychomotor abilities.

In 2013 the government began implementing a new curriculum model that was predicted as a character and competency-based curriculum. Teachers as executors in learning who directly face to learners must understand the contents of the curriculum. A correct understanding of the contents of the K-13 Curriculum is one of the successful implementation of the curriculum, so that teachers have a strategic role in the world of education.

The implementation of English learning in class can run well if there is a competent facilitator and is able to lead to Teaching and Learning Activities (KBM). The teacher as a facilitator in learning has an important role because with the

teacher the objectives, teaching materials, methods, media, and assessment can be implemented well. The existence of teachers in the teaching and learning process is very important and absolute, because the teacher is the director and actor in learning that affects the quality of learning (Sudjana, 2004). The existence of the teacher in learning to provide learning material makes it easy for students to organize the material into a pattern that has meaning.

The concepts and indicators of the above understanding are used in analyzing the results of research on teacher understanding of the the K-13 Curriculum which is a development in the previous curriculum namely CBSA and KTSP and its implementation in the teaching and learning process. Between the learning done by the teacher and the teacher's understanding of the implementation of the the K-13 Curriculum which will have implications for the teacher's understanding of the implementation of the the K-13 Curriculum so that the implementation of the the K-13 Curriculum runs optimally.

Based on the description above, the theoretical framework of this research can be drawn as follows :

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The Previous Studies

Puspitasari (2016:98) in her research on 2013 curriculum found that the teacher did an improvement in using the learning instruction based on 2013 curriculum. It helped teachers in the teaching and learning activities. Meanwhile, Sunggingwati(2013 :88) in her research' Teachers' Perception Toward the New Curriculum 2013 indicated that the teachers are confidence about the concept of the curriculum but slingly unsure how the English lesson would be taught to their students based on the new

curriculum. In addition to this, Zulhernanda (2018,p.1) in his research “Teachers’ Perceptions on Application Of 2013 Curriculum for Elementary School in Medan” asserted that the K-13 is still a lot of flaws and should need revision again. This is due to the fact that the teachers sees the condition based on what they see, what they feel, and it will be what they think

Methodology

1. Research Design

How a study is conducted is informed by the goals and research problems it investigates. Every research study certainly has particular interest and purposes. According to Sugiyono (2016), the goal or purpose of a study can be differentiated in three general classifications comprising discovery, verification, and development. A study that aims to discover is concerned with finding new data that have not been discussed or search off previously. The one that focuses on verification is trying to proof the hesitation or skepticism on a particular information or concept. Whereas a development study is concerned with extending and having a deeper understanding on the previous concept or knowledge.

As each study has different goals and purposes, the approach or method used to perform a particular study is different from one another. Depending on its goals or purposes, the methods in conducting a study can be classified into basic research method, applied research method, and research and development method. In addition, research methods are also

differentiated based on the naturalistic features of the object or the setting of a study. In this classification, research methods are divided into experimental, survey, and naturalistic research method. In both of this classification, however, all the methods stay on a continuum which means that all the methods are interconnected, and it is difficult to clearly separate one study from another.

The most well-known classification of research method is differentiated based on the two common approaches of quantitative and qualitative. A quantitative study is associated with numerical data and statistical procedure. It is usually linked with some treatments and controls involving specific procedures that are systematic and measurable. Hence, it is considered less natural but is very objective and unbiased. In contrast, a qualitative research is referred to a work in a very natural setting that aims to understand and interpret social phenomena. In this research there is no treatment or manipulation is made. The research works with individuals' opinions and views to interpret and understand meanings behind the phenomena studied. As the interpretation is made by the researchers it is considered potentially subjective but it is a particularly strong method to explore social issues naturally.

In educational research, the main concern is to explore or investigate a particular educational issue or debate that can contribute to improving educational practices. Here, research plays very vital roles as it helps educators to develop

competencies and skills. Furthermore, it also informs policy and decision making on a particular debates in education which can lead to a better quality education. Like any research in general, educational research is also performed in different approaches and various research designs based on research problems studied. Among research designs associated with quantitative and qualitative approaches in educational research comprises experimental, correlational, survey, ethnographic, grounded theory, narrative, mixed method, and action research design.

The current study has two main objectives. First, it aims to explore and understand the perception of English language teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh about the implementation of K-13. Second, it intends to figure out obstacles and challenges they face in implementing K-13 in English language teaching and learning process. For these purposes, the researchers collect some measurable data and also record teachers' opinion related to the implementation of K-13. Hence, the study is performed both in a quantitative and qualitative approach. However, the study did not implement any treatment neither control the situation. It collected data in their natural setting and did not make any intervention. Furthermore, the result of the study is described narratively based on a number of themes emerged. Extracts from teachers' interview are used as the remarks that highlight the themes found. Thus, the study is employing a narrative design in a more qualitative approach nature.

2. Participants

The subject of the current study are English language teachers in Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh. There are five sub-districts chosen as the location of the study, they are; Aceh Barat, Aceh Jaya, Nagan Raya, Aceh Barat Daya, and Aceh Selatan. There are a total of 25 Madrasah Aliyah within this South West Region of Aceh comprising of 10 state Madrasah and 15 private Madrasah. Due to the limitation of the study, it could not cover all of the existing madrasahs. Accordingly, it put more attention to state madrasah considering that they have the obligation to implement the current curriculum and are monitored and supervised by the educational authority. However, a few private madrasah were also included to enrich data needed.

Creswell (2008) pointed that in a qualitative study, the participants are identified from those who can be very helpful and highly informative for the study. The researchers can determine the participants of their study purposefully based on the information and data they want to obtain. A sampling strategy used by researchers is closely linked to specific information they plan to present in reporting the result of the study. The current study intends to record various perspective of the English language teachers' on the implementation of K-13. In this case, maximal variation was employed as the sampling strategy in determining the participant of the study. Hence, all the English teachers, from a total of 10 state madrasah and 4 private

madrasah visited as the subject of study, were recruited as the participants of the study. There were 21 English language teachers in total with different range of teaching experience. Most of them are civil servant (PNS) (19). Only a few of them (2) who are non-PNS teachers.

For participants convenient, ethical issues were also well thought out. Creswell explained that collecting data in a qualitative project likely requires participants to share private information in detail to the researchers. For this high trust level relation to form, researchers need to take account on some ethical practices that include informing the participants the purpose of study, avoiding dishonest practices, sharing information about the researchers, respecting the research site, reciprocity, using ethical interview practices, keeping confidentiality, and working together with the participants.

Before initiating data collection procedure, the participants were informed about the purpose of the study. Furthermore, data confidentiality were guaranteed through a letter of informant request and a consent form that clearly explained about the study being conducted and the participants' rights when taking part in the study. To appreciate participants' time and insight, a note book was given to each participant as a token of appreciation after data collection period was completed.

3. Instrument

There are two research instruments utilized to collect data, questionnaire and individual interview. Questionnaire contains a series of questions or statements with multiple choice options, rating scale, or checklist items that can easily collect information from a large group of participant. It is usually presented in close form questions or statements, but it can also formatted as open ended questions or statements.

In the current study, the questionnaire was used in the first stage of data collection process. This questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part one contains 32 statements that are related to the implementation of K-13 meanwhile part two collects participants personal background information. The items in part one cover four major themes that include teaching and learning activity, teacher's understanding of K-13, challenges and difficulties in implementing K-13, and types of assessment the teachers use with K-13. All the items in part one are close ended statement that were presented in six rating scale. The scale ranges from 6 as strongly agree, 5 agree, 4 slightly agree, 3 slightly disagree, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly disagree. As part two of the questionnaire deals with participants' background information, the items were presented as open-ended. The participants were asked to provide some personal information that include: their affiliation, age, teaching experience, the length of K-13 implementation in their respective school, their current

status as a teacher, and K-13 related trainings they have attended. Appendix 1 shows detail questionnaire used for the study.

The second instrument, the interview was used at the second stage of data collection. The interview was conducted to pursue a more in depth understanding of how the English language teachers perceive K-13. In many research guideline book, interview is pointed as a popular data collection technique in a qualitative study in addition to observation, documents, and audiovisual materials (Moleong and Lexy, 2005). The open questions asked during the interview enable participants to response freely, and speak up their mind or share their experience without being constrained by other perspectives. The researchers also can have a good control over the information they expect to obtain by clarifying or elaborating with more specific questions when the participants seem to be confused or get away in answering the questions. Nevertheless, interview is not as simple as it sounds. It requires special skill to build trust between the interviewer and the interviewee. It is important to assure for confidentiality of all the information given and to provide comfort for the participants by asking all the questions in a relax mode. In addition, the researchers need to be cautious for dishonest information and filtered responses that might be given due to the influence of their presence during the face to face interview session.

The interview was carried face to face on one by one where the researchers sit together with one participant at a time.

This interview was only performed with several participants that were considered able to provide good information about K-13. They were selected based on the background information given in the questionnaire that shows their teaching experience as well as trainings related to K-13 they have ever had. There are five semi structured questions were used as guideline questions in the interview. However, the researchers always clarify and elaborate the questions in more details when they were asked to each participant. The questions cover around what the teacher perception of K-13 is, what challenges and difficulties they face in implementing-13, how the teaching and learning process is performed within K-13, and how and what type of assessment they use. Each interview lasted within 15-20 minutes, and all the session was recorded using a digital recorder. To avoid losing important information, some notes were also taken during this individual interview. All the interviews were transcribed so that all the information given can be more transparent and can be analyzed in details.

Table 1. Type of Instrument and Data Collected

No	Type of Intrument	Data Collected
1	Questionnaire	Teachers perception of K-13 including:
		1. Teaching and learning activity in K-13
		2. Teacher understanding of K-13
		3. Difficulties and challenges

		4. Type of assessment used
2	Interview	In depth exploration of teachers' perception of K-13

4. Procedure

Data collection was performed from August to September 2019. It started from Aceh Barat district followed by Aceh Jaya and Nagan Raya. After finishing with these three districts, data collection was continued to Aceh Barat Daya and Aceh Selatan. The researchers along with a research assistant visited 2 to 3 Madrasah Aliyah in each subdistricts. In the first stage, data collection process focuses on distributing questionnaire to all English teachers in each school that was visited. Prior to distributing the questionnaire to the English teachers, the researchers met the headmaster in each school to inform about the study that is being conducted and let him/her know that the study has been approved by the local office of Ministry of Religious Affairs in the district.

Having completed the administration matters with the headmaster, the researchers met the teachers to distribute the questionnaire. As it is important to encourage honest responses from each participant, prior to the interview the researchers tried to create a friendly atmosphere and a relax situation. In this attempt, the researchers briefed the teachers that the study is important to develop a better curriculum and English language teaching in Indonesia, and that their inputs would be very valuable. Furthermore, they were ensured that would be no

judgment made regarding the answers and responses they provided. The teachers were also reminded that any negative or positive responses will be equally important inputs for the study. Lastly, all the teachers were informed that confidentiality of data given would be maintained, so they were urged to speak up their experience freely without any anxiety. Afterwards, the interview was started with a small talk about the teachers' day and further moved into specific questions about the implementation of K-13 in English language teaching.

The second stage of data collection which is the interview was conducted at the second week of September after the completion of the questionnaire. As it is intended to obtain a more indepth understanding of teachers perception about K-13 implementation in English language teaching, only a few teachers who were considered able to represent the condition in each district were interviewed. Each interview last about 15 to 25 minutes. The interview was recorded using a digital recorder to avoid losing important information. All the teachers were once more reminded about the confidentiality of data and guaranteed that no personal information will be revealed. Any information used for publication need will be pseudonym. Finally, the researchers thanked all the teachers for their voluntary involvement in the study, presented a notebook as a small gift to appreciate their time and infomation.

Figure 2. Research Procedure

5. Data Analysis

As the current study collects both qualitative and quantitative data, the data analysis was performed in both ways. Analyzing quantitative data certainly involves statistics calculation. Although it is generally perceived challenging for those who struggle with math, the process can be done well with the help of some computer programs. Nevertheless, as Creswell (2008) noted, this process does require some preparations and data organization. Among the steps to do are scoring data, determining types of data, selecting a statistical program, inputting data, dealing with missing data, and lastly, conducting the analysis.

Sugiyono pointed that there are two common types of statistics calculation; descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The first one deals with the description of the data in

terms of general tendencies, the spread of scores, or the comparison of score relation to one another. The calculation, however, focuses on a particular variable that generally is not intended for generalization purposes. On another hand, inferential statistics is used to compare or relate two or more independent variables to dependent variables. It is also meant to test the hypotheses about the differences or relationship among the group of variables in which the result will be generalized to the whole population.

Since the questionnaire is the only quantitative data of the current study, the analysis was performed through descriptive statistics. It is meant to get the general description of teachers' perception about the implementation of K-13 in English language learning. The data was calculated to get the average mean in each elements related to K-13 implementation.

Different from quantitative analysis, qualitative analysis does not involve statistical calculation. However, it requires a good skill in summarizing and interpreting. Creswell stated, "Analyzing qualitative data requires understanding to make sense of text and images...". Many novice qualitative researchers may find the process challenging as it involves a large amount of data. Nevertheless, by following the procedure properly, data analysis can be managed well by every researcher.

Moleong explained that data analysis in qualitative studies began with reducing the amount of data by abstracting all the information obtained. This abstraction is performed by

making conclusion from each source of information and coding them with a number of short statements. The next step is to group the codes into some categorizations of theme. The final step is to assure the saturation of themes emerged by checking back all the data and making sure that no new information arise.

With the improvement of technology, qualitative researchers these days can analyze their data using computer, or alternately do a manual data analysis by hand if the amount of data is reasonably manageable. It depends on what accesses and resources are available for them. Since the database for the current study was small (less than 500 pages of script), data analysis was performed manually instead of utilizing computer. The researchers wanted to be close to data to have a real sense of participants' responses. Furthermore, the researchers have no experience in using computer software analysis. Hence, manual analysis was believed to be more effective.

In the current study, the researchers begin the analysis by having all the recorded interviews transcribed. The researchers then read the transcriptions and coded them by highlighting some segments and writing a number of short statements in the margin that had been purposely left in the script. During the coding process, ideas or themes that come to mind were also noted down in the opposite margin as the initial themes to be used later. After the coding process was completed, the researchers summarized the codes and developed the common themes that represented all information obtain from the transcripts. In the final step of data

analysis, the researchers re-read the transcription both from individual interview and focus group discussion, compare the themes emerged in both and decide the final themes as the main findings of the study. In general, the coding process to analyze the data was carried on following a visual model from Creswell.

Figure 3: Creswell's visual model of the coding process in qualitative research

Results and Discussions

This chapter describes the data from questionnaires and interview about English teachers' perspectives toward the implementation of K13 in Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh.

1. Findings

1.1.1. Data From Questionnaire.

There were 32 questions stated in the questionnaires. Those 32 questions dealt with English teacher perception on the K-13 in form of teaching and learning process, grading variety

and obstacles faced by English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh.

The first category was about English teacher perspective on teaching and learning process with the K-13. There were 15 statements given by researchers. Those are (1) have confidence in teaching, (2) learning fun, (3) develop critical thinking students, (4) create active and participatory students, (5) develop communicative ability of students, (6) increase and develop 4 macro skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading), (7) know and appreciate students skill, (8) students and teachers book, (9) learning motivation, (10) learning media, (11) giving task, (12) changing curriculum, (13) understanding about curriculum, (14) comparison between the K-13 and the 2006 curriculum, (15) the K-13 is about ability, knowledge, and attitude of students.

In addition, there were only six respondents who get very strong perception toward the implementation of K13 in Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh. Meanwhile, there are 13 respondents who are included “strong” interpretation on understanding the implementation. of the K-13 and the last remaining is 1 respondent who gets “enough” interpretation.

The second category was about English teacher perspective on grading variety with the K-13. There were 8 statements given by researchers. Those are (1) fair attitude in evaluating, (2) assess students’ spesific attitudes and skills, (3) assessment technique, (4) using journal, (5) written test, (6) oral test, (7) homework, and (8) role play. Half of all respondents have

very strong perception on grading variety with the K-13, and the highest score is 94%. Nearly nine out of twenty respondents in the South West Region of Aceh have strong interpretation. However, there is one respondent who get enough interpretation.

The third category was about obstacles faced by English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh. There were 9 statements given by researchers. Those are (1) analyze SKL, KI, and KD, (2) assess students output and input, (3) national examination, (4) administrative requirements, (5) analyze students and teacher book, (6) require the teachers to be creative, (7) communicative ability students, (8) material, and (9) difficulty learning language.

Overall, there are three interpretations on obstacles faced by English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh such as very strong, strong, and enough. Nearly six out of twenty respondents have very strong obstacle in implementing the K-13, at around 81 to 83 percent. In addition, there are seven respondents who include “strong” interpretation. It means that they have 63 percent to 74 percent of obstacle in implementing the K-13. The last, there are seven respondents are in enough interpretation.

1.2.1 Data From Interview.

The following is the data of the interview with the 7 respondents in which the researchers asked 3 questions about

English teachers perspective with the K-13 regarding on teaching and learning process, grading, and obstacles.

1.2.2 English Teacher Perspective with the K-13 Regarding on Teaching and Learning Process.

Regarding English teacher perspective with the K-13 on teaching and learning process, the respondents gave their answer variously. Below is the excerpts from the interview, as follow :

Teacher 1 : “The K-13 is interesting than previous curriculum. For students who have good language skill, the K-13 is good for them. In addition, the teachers are also enthusiast to make teaching media to fulfill the needs of 4C aspects (communicative, collaborative, and others)”.

Teacher 2 :”In my opinion, K 13 is good, but we know that there is always changes in curriculum. We, as teachers especially in Islamic School is not well prepared as they are in other schools. In those schools, they are well prepared before implementing the curriculum, but not in here. Thus, we as teachers here are facing some difficulties in understanding K13 itself. It makes us looking for answers from other public schools, SMA. It is because teachers in SMA had have prepared. They know what K13 is as

well as the way to implement it, meanwhile we don't. Well, K13 is good but we know that nothing is perfect. All curriculum are created based on situation in each school”

Teacher 3 : “There is team teaching in the teaching-learning session and it has been applied in K13, but the number of it is not pleasant. For me myself, K13 is more fun than the previous ones, which focus on knowledge only. In English subject, the students become more communicative, but still it depends on the students themselves”

1.2.3 Obstacles Faced by English Teachers of Madrasah Aliyah in the South West Region of Aceh.

Regarding the obstacles faced by the English teachers of in the South West Region of Aceh in implementing the K-13. This is presented by Teacher 2, 3, and 7's comments:

Teacher 2 : “The obstacles in K13 is making the students master the things. They have to be capable enough. For example the material about English Structure/ grammar. There is no special time to explain, we just use the reading material and teach it integratedly. We just teach

it whether the students could take it in holistic way or not”

Teacher 3 : “What makes it's harder is the additional works to do, the attributes are too many’

Teacher 4 : “Sometimes, we are not ready in this situation such as in administration with the 2013 currciculum and there are many things to do in this curriculum’

Teacher 6 : “The big obstacle I faced is observing the students. Observing when they are aksing question is the example, we become challenged to find what learning material to prepare for them. At least, there is fun video related to the material to attract them, creative materials, and observe how the students responding to those materials. In short, we have to be well-prepared in each teaching sessions, to attract them to ask some questions. This is the first challenge for me. Second, is to motivate them. Because this is kind of rural area, not an uptown area which the passion of students are below the average. It is my challenge to motivate them by using interesting teaching media. It is different from KTSP in previous, we just gave the material and leave it that way”

2. Discussions

There are some findings that are encountered by the researchers during and after the data collection.

The first finding is that the 20 respondents in this study are still confused with the learning system by using the K-13. In fact, almost half of respondents have not yet received training about the K-13 so that they get different perspective about the K-13. This finding is in line with Lewis and Anne (2008) who found that the implementation of Curriculum 2013 has not been effective. In addition, the teacher try to finish all Basic Competence (KD) in one semester. Eventhough, the allocation time is insufficient.

The second finding is the respondents feel that there are too many forms of assessment required such as peer assessment, affective assessment, psychomotor assessment required for students. This is a burden because there are too many students in one class such as 35 to 40 students in one class. In addition, the teacher should make the descriptions about every single development in the class. The third finding is the respondents claim that the biggest obstacle in implementing the K-13 is the excessive administrative demands.

Conclusion

There are some problems faced by English teachers in implementing K-13:

- a. The majority of English teachers in the South West Aceh still feel confused in implementing the K-13. This might contribute the out put of the teaching-learning program which is not effective.
- b. Some of English teachers in the South West Aceh do not receive adequate training related to K-13. As the result, they have no idea what and how to teach English using K-13.
- c. The English teachers also face difficulties with time constraint. This causes the English teachers have to rush their lesson plan in order to achieve the target of the teaching
- d. The K-13 has led English teachers to do alot of forms of assessment required such as peer assessment, affective assessment, psychomotor assessment required for students.

Recommendation

- a. The government of Indonesia, in this matter, the Deparment of Education has to ascertain that the majority of English teachers receive training related to K-13.
- b. The Department needs to review the time allocation provided to the English teachers. If it is not enough, then they have to some changes on that meet teachers' expectation.

- c. The English teachers should be creative and innovative in improving their understanding on K-13 using printed and online resources.

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